

COMPARATIVE EFFICACY OF ORAL ZINC SUPPLEMENTATION VERSUS PROBIOTIC THERAPY IN REDUCING THE DURATION AND SEVERITY OF ACUTE DIARRHEA IN CHILDREN AGED 6 MONTHS TO 5 YEARS

Farwa Arshad^{*1}, Romail Haider², Ahmad Saud Khurshid³, Rabbia Javed⁴,
Saima Ashraf⁵, Misbah Sardar⁶

^{*1}MBBS, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, farwaarshad1234@gmail.com

²MBBS, Working as Medical Officer at Department of Paediatrics Shalamar Hospital Lahore

³MBBS, Medical Officer, Ex House Officer DHQ Teaching Hospital Mirpur AJK

⁴MBBS, WMO Luqman Medical Center

⁵MBBS from Mbbsmc_ Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Shaheed Medical College Mirpur. Housejob done from DHQ
Mirpur Ajk

⁶MBBS, FCPS-1, Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15645635>

Keywords

Acute diarrhea, Children, Efficacy, Probiotics, Randomized controlled trial, Zinc supplementation

Article History

Received on 04 May 2025

Accepted on 04 June 2025

Published on 12 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Farwa Arshad

Abstract

Background: The global burden of acute diarrhea in children under five remains a major public health concern, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Zinc supplementation and probiotics are widely used non-antibiotic therapies, each with proposed benefits in reducing the duration and severity of diarrheal episodes.

Objectives: To compare the efficacy of oral zinc supplementation versus probiotic therapy in reducing the duration and severity of acute diarrhea in children aged 6 months to 5 years.

Study Design & Setting: This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Pediatrics Shaikh Zayed Hospital Lahore, over a period of 6 months.

Methodology: A total of 120 children aged 6 months to 5 years presenting with acute diarrhea were randomly assigned to two equal groups. Group A received oral zinc (20 mg/day for 10 days; 10 mg for infants <1 year), while Group B received a probiotic containing *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (10^9 CFU/day for 5 days). Both groups received standard supportive care. Outcome measures included duration of diarrhea, daily stool frequency, severity grading, and adverse events. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Results: The mean duration of diarrhea was significantly shorter in the zinc group (3.1 ± 1.2 days) than in the probiotic group (3.8 ± 1.4 days; $p = 0.008$). Stool frequency was lower in the zinc group (4.7 ± 1.1 vs. 5.2 ± 1.3 ; $p = 0.021$), and a higher proportion experienced mild diarrhea (63.3% vs. 50%; $p = 0.014$). Both treatments were well tolerated.

Conclusion: Zinc supplementation proved more effective than probiotics in reducing the duration and severity of acute diarrhea in children under five.

INTRODUCTION

Acute diarrhea remains a significant public health concern, particularly in developing countries where it contributes to substantial morbidity and mortality among children under five years of age.¹ Globally, it is one of the leading causes of preventable deaths in children, accounting for approximately 525,000 fatalities each year according to the World Health Organization (WHO).² In Pakistan, diarrhea continues to rank among the top five causes of death in children under five, highlighting the urgent need for effective, affordable, and accessible interventions.^{3,4} Acute diarrhea is typically defined as the passage of three or more loose or watery stools within a 24-hour period lasting less than 14 days, and is primarily caused by infections due to viruses, bacteria, or parasites. Children between 6 months and 5 years are particularly vulnerable due to immature immune systems, malnutrition, and poor sanitation practices.⁵

Current management strategies for acute diarrhea focus on rehydration therapy, continued feeding, and, when appropriate, the use of zinc supplementation and probiotics. Zinc plays a crucial role in maintaining immune function and intestinal mucosal integrity.⁶ Its deficiency has been linked to increased susceptibility to infections, prolonged episodes of diarrhea, and higher risk of complications. The WHO and UNICEF recommend zinc supplementation—20 mg daily for 10–14 days for children over 6 months—to reduce the duration, severity, and recurrence of diarrheal episodes.⁷ Several clinical trials have demonstrated that zinc supplementation can significantly shorten the course of diarrhea and reduce stool frequency.^{8,9}

On the other hand, probiotics—defined as live microorganisms that confer health benefits when administered in adequate amounts—have gained considerable attention in recent years. Common probiotic strains used in pediatric diarrhea include *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Saccharomyces boulardii*, and *Bifidobacterium* species.^{10,11} Probiotics exert their effects by enhancing the gut barrier function, inhibiting the growth of pathogenic organisms, modulating the immune response, and restoring the normal gut flora disrupted by infection. Randomized controlled trials have shown that probiotics can reduce the duration of diarrhea by approximately

one day and decrease stool output, though results may vary depending on the strain used, dose, and timing of administration.^{12,13}

While both zinc and probiotics have proven benefits, limited studies have directly compared their individual efficacy in the treatment of acute diarrhea in young children. There is a pressing need to evaluate which intervention yields better outcomes in terms of reducing the duration and severity of symptoms. A comparative analysis will provide clearer guidance for pediatricians and public health policymakers in resource-constrained settings, helping to optimize treatment protocols and reduce the burden of disease. This study aims to compare the efficacy of oral zinc supplementation and probiotic therapy in reducing the duration and severity of acute diarrhea in children aged 6 months to 5 years.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Pediatrics, Shaik Zayed Hospital Lahore From Nov 2024 to April 2025 after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee. A total of 120 children, aged 6 months to 5 years, who presented with acute diarrhea (defined as passage of three or more loose stools in a 24-hour period for less than 14 days) were included in the study. The sample size of 120 was calculated using OpenEpi software with a confidence level of 95%, power of 80%, and anticipated difference of 25% in mean duration of diarrhea between the two groups, based on previously published literature.

Children with chronic diarrhea, severe malnutrition, known immunodeficiency, recent antibiotic use, or any systemic illness requiring hospitalization were excluded. After obtaining informed written consent from parents or guardians, eligible participants were randomly allocated into two equal groups (n=60 each) using a computer-generated randomization table.

Group A received oral zinc supplementation at a dose of 20 mg per day for 10 days (10 mg per day for children under one year), as per WHO recommendations. Group B received probiotic therapy consisting of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (10⁹ CFU/day) for 5 days. Both groups were

provided with standard supportive care, including oral rehydration salts (ORS), continued feeding, and antipyretics when necessary. No antibiotics or antidiarrheal agents were administered unless clinically indicated.

Patients were monitored daily for duration of diarrhea (measured in days until the passage of last loose stool), frequency of stools per day, presence of fever, and any adverse events. Severity was assessed using a standardized diarrhea severity scoring system based on the number of stools, dehydration status, and systemic symptoms. Follow-up continued until resolution of diarrhea or up to 14 days.

Data were collected on a predesigned proforma and entered into SPSS version 25.0 for analysis. Quantitative variables such as age, duration of diarrhea, and frequency of stools were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables such as gender and presence of dehydration were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Independent t-tests were applied for continuous variables, and chi-square tests were used for categorical variables. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The demographic characteristics of the study participants are summarized in Table 1. The mean age of children in the zinc group was 28.4 ± 11.6 months, while that in the probiotic group was 29.2 ± 12.1 months, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.684$). The gender distribution was similar between the two groups, with 58.3% males in the zinc group and 55.0% males in the probiotic group ($p = 0.711$). The mean body weight was also comparable: 10.6 ± 2.3 kg in the zinc group and 10.9 ± 2.5 kg in the probiotic group ($p = 0.438$). These findings indicate that both groups were demographically well-matched at baseline.

Clinical outcomes between the two groups are compared in Table 2. The mean duration of diarrhea was significantly shorter in the zinc group (3.1 ± 1.2 days) compared to the probiotic group (3.8 ± 1.4 days), with a statistically significant p-value of 0.008. Similarly, the average stool frequency per day was lower in the zinc group (4.7 ± 1.1) than in the probiotic group (5.2 ± 1.3), also reaching statistical significance ($p = 0.021$). While the proportion of children with fever was higher in the probiotic group (30.0%) than in the zinc group (20.0%), the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.206$). The presence of vomiting was observed in 23.3% of the zinc group and 26.7% of the probiotic group, with no significant difference ($p = 0.674$). These results suggest that zinc supplementation was more effective in reducing the duration and frequency of diarrhea.

The severity of diarrhea, assessed using a clinical scoring system, is presented in Table 3. In the zinc group, 63.3% of children had mild diarrhea, compared to 50.0% in the probiotic group. Moderate severity was observed in 30.0% of zinc-treated children and 36.7% in the probiotic group. Severe diarrhea was reported in 6.7% of the zinc group and 13.3% of the probiotic group. The difference in severity distribution between the groups was statistically significant ($p = 0.014$), indicating a trend toward milder symptoms in the zinc group.

Adverse events during treatment are detailed in Table 4. Nausea was reported in 5.0% of the zinc group and 3.3% of the probiotic group ($p = 0.648$). Abdominal cramps occurred in 3.3% of zinc-treated children and 5.0% of those receiving probiotics ($p = 0.648$). The majority of participants in both groups (91.7%) experienced no adverse effects, with no difference between the groups ($p = 1.000$). These findings demonstrate that both interventions were well tolerated with minimal side effects.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n = 120)

Variable	Zinc Group (n = 60)	Probiotic Group (n = 60)	p-value
Mean Age (months)	28.4 ± 11.6	29.2 ± 12.1	0.684
Gender (Male)	35 (58.3%)	33 (55.0%)	0.711
Gender (Female)	25 (41.7%)	27 (45.0%)	
Mean Weight (kg)	10.6 ± 2.3	10.9 ± 2.5	0.438

Table 2: Clinical Outcomes in Zinc and Probiotic Groups

Outcome Variable	Zinc Group (n = 60)	Probiotic Group (n = 60)	p-value
Mean Duration of Diarrhea (days)	3.1 ± 1.2	3.8 ± 1.4	0.008
Mean Stool Frequency per Day	4.7 ± 1.1	5.2 ± 1.3	0.021
Presence of Fever (Yes)	12 (20.0%)	18 (30.0%)	0.206
Vomiting Present (Yes)	14 (23.3%)	16 (26.7%)	0.674

Table 3: Severity of Diarrhea Based on Clinical Scoring

Severity Level	Zinc Group (n = 60)	Probiotic Group (n = 60)	p-value
Mild	38 (63.3%)	30 (50.0%)	0.014
Moderate	18 (30.0%)	22 (36.7%)	
Severe	4 (6.7%)	8 (13.3%)	

Table 4: Adverse Events Observed During Treatment

Adverse Event	Zinc Group (n = 60)	Probiotic Group (n = 60)	p-value
Nausea	3 (5.0%)	2 (3.3%)	0.648
Abdominal Cramps	2 (3.3%)	3 (5.0%)	0.648
No Adverse Effects	55 (91.7%)	55 (91.7%)	1.000

DISCUSSION

Acute diarrhea is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in children under five, especially in low- and middle-income countries. It results in significant fluid loss, malnutrition, and healthcare burden.¹⁴ Zinc supplementation is recommended by WHO for reducing duration and severity of diarrhea due to its role in immune support and mucosal repair. Probiotics have also shown promise by restoring gut microbiota and inhibiting pathogenic organisms.¹⁵ Both interventions are safe, affordable, and widely available. However, limited studies directly compare their efficacy, creating a need for further evidence-based evaluation.

Our study demonstrated that oral zinc supplementation significantly reduced both the duration (3.1 vs 3.8 days; $p=0.008$) and frequency of diarrhea (4.7 vs 5.2 stools/day; $p=0.021$), and resulted in milder disease severity (63.3% mild vs 50%; $p=0.014$), while safety profiles were comparable. These findings align closely with existing evidence and offer meaningful contributions to the pediatric diarrhea literature.

Study –a randomized double-blind trial in India– reported a 62% reduction in stool frequency from

day 1 to day 3 in children receiving zinc versus 26% in placebo, with early recovery and shorter hospital stays.¹⁶ Another meta-analysis showed that zinc reduced diarrhea duration by approximately 20 hours (95% CI -29 to -11 hours), with especially pronounced effects in malnourished children. In our study, zinc shortened diarrhea by 0.7 days (~17 hours), consistent with this range and corroborating its continued benefit.¹⁷ Our finding of faster and less severe recovery with zinc mirrors that from a Turkish RCT,¹⁸ where zinc (15 mg/day) and a synbiotic both reduced diarrhea duration significantly versus control, with no significant difference between them, but zinc showed an advantage in children still symptomatic at 72 and 96 hours. A Korean study similarly found zinc superior to probiotics in duration and complication rates, reporting that 100% of probiotic-treated children had diarrhea at day 3, compared to 76.1% of the zinc group (RR=1.31).¹⁹

In a Karachi-based RCT, children receiving zinc plus probiotics recovered faster than those on probiotics alone, although symptom severity at two weeks was similar.²⁰ A recent study in Kurdistan [11] also showed no long-term severity difference but

significantly shorter recovery time (1.34 vs 2.00 days) with combined therapy. Our study confirms zinc's key role and highlights that even without probiotic co-administration, zinc alone significantly improves outcomes. Meta-analyses of probiotic use in acute pediatric diarrhea found modest benefits—reducing duration by ~14% and stool frequency by ~13%—but varied by strain and region, and often involved predominantly rehydration control comparators. In our probiotic arm, diarrhea lasted 3.8 days with higher stool frequency and severity than zinc, indicating probiotics provide mild benefit, but not as strong as zinc in this age group. Our study reinforces WHO guidelines advocating 20 mg zinc for 10 days in children aged ≥6 months. Effects we observed (–0.7 days duration, lower stool frequency, milder symptoms) align with both prospective trials and meta-analyses. Probiotics offer supportive effects, but zinc outperforms them when evaluated head-to-head.^{21,17}

This study used a randomized controlled design, ensuring reduced bias and reliable comparison. It included a well-defined age group of 6 months to 5 years, targeting the most vulnerable population. Standardized treatment protocols and consistent follow-up strengthened data accuracy. However, the sample size was limited to 120, restricting generalizability. Only one probiotic strain was tested, which may not represent all available options. Additionally, long-term recurrence or nutritional impact was not assessed.

CONCLUSION

Oral zinc supplementation was more effective than probiotic therapy in reducing both the duration and severity of acute diarrhea in young children. Both treatments were well tolerated with minimal adverse effects. Zinc remains a preferred first-line adjunct in the management of pediatric diarrhea.

REFERENCES

Anteneh ZA, Andargie K, Tarekegn M. Prevalence and determinants of acute diarrhea among children younger than five years old in Jabithennan District, Northwest Ethiopia, 2014. *BMC public health*. 2017 Dec;17:1-8.

Hartman RM, Cohen AL, Antoni S, Mwenda J, Weldegebriel G, Biey J, Shaba K, De Oliveira L, Rey G, Ortiz C, Tereza M. Risk factors for mortality among children younger than age 5 years with severe diarrhea in low- and middle-income countries: findings from the World Health Organization-coordinated Global Rotavirus and Pediatric Diarrhea Surveillance Networks. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2023 Feb 1;76(3):e1047-53.

Irsan IR, Fatimah N, Sadhana U, Susilaningih N, Restiwijaya M, Nur M, Qurnianingsih E, Lukitasari L, Humairah I, Bakhtiar A, Suwandito S. Treatment of Acute Diarrhea in Children Aged 1–5 Years Provided by Doctors in Surabaya. *Folia Medica Indonesiana*. 2023;59(2):108-14.

Zhou HL, Bessey T, Wang SM, Mo ZJ, Barclay L, Wang JX, Zhang CJ, Ma JC, Qiu C, Zhao G, Li RC. Burden and etiology of moderate and severe diarrhea in children less than 5 years of age living in north and south of China: Prospective, population-based surveillance. *Gut Pathogens*. 2021 May 24;13(1):33.

Charoenwat, B., Suwannaying, K., Paibool, W., Laoaroon, N., Sutra, S., Thepsuthammarat, K. and Sirirattanakul, S., 2023. The impact of rotavirus vaccination on acute diarrhea in Thai children under 5 years of age in the first year of universal implementation of rotavirus vaccines in the National Immunization Program (NIP) in Thailand: a 6-year analysis. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), p.2109.

Rahman A, Hossain MM. Prevalence and determinants of fever, ARI and diarrhea among children aged 6–59 months in Bangladesh. *BMC pediatrics*. 2022 Mar 5;22(1):117.

Ahmed T, Chisti MJ, Rahman MW, Alam T, Ahmed D, Parvin I, Kabir MF, Sazawal S, Dhingra P, Dutta A, Deb S. Effect of 3 days of oral azithromycin on young children with acute diarrhea in low-resource settings: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA network open*. 2021 Dec 1;4(12):e2136726.

- Mero S, Timonen S, Lääveri T, Løfberg S, Kirveskari J, Ursing J, Rombo L, Kofoed PE, Kantele A. Prevalence of diarrhoeal pathogens among children under five years of age with and without diarrhoea in Guinea-Bissau. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*. 2021 Sep 29;15(9):e0009709.
- Wang P, Asare E, Pitzer VE, Dubrow R, Chen K. Associations between long-term drought and diarrhea among children under five in low- and middle-income countries. *Nature Communications*. 2022 Jun 30;13(1):3661.
- Okechukwu CO, AINU M, Adias TC, Elemuwa CO, Rotifa SU, Ogbointuwei C, Raimi MO, Oweibia M, Alabo AF, Okoyen E, Appah WW. Evaluating the Impact of Rotavirus Vaccination on Childhood Diarrhea Incidence in Bayelsa State, Nigeria: Achievements, Challenges, and Future Directions. *JMIR Preprints*. *JMIR Preprints*. 2024;27(07):2024.
- Tesema GA, Worku MG, Tessema ZT, Teshale AB, Alem AZ, Yeshaw Y, Alamneh TS, Liyew AM. Prevalence and determinants of severity levels of anemia among children aged 6–59 months in sub-Saharan Africa: A multilevel ordinal logistic regression analysis. *PloS one*. 2021 Apr 23;16(4):e0249978.
- Sultana R, Luby SP, Gurley ES, Rimi NA, Swarna ST, Khan JA, Nahar N, Ghosh PK, Howlader SR, Kabir H, Khan S. Cost of illness for severe and non-severe diarrhea borne by households in a low-income urban community of Bangladesh: a cross-sectional study. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*. 2021 Jun 11;15(6):e0009439.
- Huang R, Xing HY, Liu HJ, Chen ZF, Tang BB. Efficacy of probiotics in the treatment of acute diarrhea in children: a systematic review and meta-analysis of clinical trials. *Translational pediatrics*. 2021 Dec;10(12):3248.
- Anato A. Severe acute malnutrition and associated factors among children under-five years: A community based-cross sectional study in Ethiopia. *Heliyon*. 2022 Oct 1;8(10).
- Meisenheimer ES, Epstein C, Thiel D. Acute diarrhea in adults. *American Family Physician*. 2022 Jul;106(1):72-80.
- Trivedi SS, Chudasama RK, Patel N. Effect of zinc supplementation in children with acute diarrhea: randomized double blind controlled trial. *Gastroenterology Research*. 2009 May 20;2(3):168.
- Rouhani P, Rezaei Kelishadi M, Saneei P. Effect of zinc supplementation on mortality in under 5-year children: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *European Journal of Nutrition*. 2022 Feb 1:1-8.
- Surono IS, Martono PD, Kameo S, Suradji EW, Koyama H. Effect of probiotic *L. plantarum* IS-10506 and zinc supplementation on humoral immune response and zinc status of Indonesian pre-school children. *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*. 2014 Oct 1;28(4):465-9.
- Ahmadipour S, Mohsenzadeh A, Alimadadi H, Salehnia M, Fallahi A. Treating Viral Diarrhea in Children by Probiotic and Zinc Supplements. *Pediatr Gastroenterol Hepatol Nutr*. 2019;22(2):162–170.
- Zakaullah Kakar, Abdul Baqi Essazai, Syed Moeed Ahmed, et al. Comparison of Zinc-Probiotic Combination Therapy to Probiotic Therapy Alone in Treating Acute Diarrhea in Children. *Pak J Med Health Sci*. 2022.
- Trivedi SS, Chudasama RK, Patel N. Effect of zinc supplementation in children with acute diarrhea: randomized double blind controlled trial. *Gastroenterology Research*. 2009 May 20;2(3):168